

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS, AND INFORMATICS

IT FOLLOWS FROM THE SPECIAL THEORY OF RELATIVITY THAT THE INVISIBLE
AFTERLIFE WORLD PREDICTED BY ALL RELIGIONS ACTUALLY PHYSICALLY EXISTS¹

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Abstract

The article proves that the generally accepted version of the special theory relativity (SRT), which states that imaginary numbers are physically unreal and therefore our only visible universe exists, is incorrect. Experimental evidence of the incorrectness of the postulated principle of not exceeding the speed of light of the SRT, from which this conclusion was drawn, is given. Therefore, a corrected version of the SRT has been created, in which this incorrect postulate is replaced by the experimentally proven principle of the physical reality of imaginary numbers. She argues that in addition to our visible universe, there are many other mutually invisible universes in nature. And they form the actually physically existing invisible afterlife world predicted by all religions.

Keywords: imaginary numbers, special theory of relativity, invisible universes, invisible afterlife world.

Introduction

Imaginary numbers, discovered about 500 years ago by Scipione Del Ferro, Niccolo Fontana Tartaglia, Gerolamo Cardano, Lodovico Ferrari and Raphael Bombelli [1], are known to everyone and are currently used in all the exact sciences. They are even studied in school mathematics courses. But unlike other numbers that are understandable to everyone - integers and fractions, positive and negative, scalar and vector, etc. - their physical essence has not yet been explained. Indeed, what is 2 kg., 3 m., 4 sec. is clear to everyone, but what is $2i$ kg., $3i$ m., $4i$ sec. where $i = \sqrt{-1}$, no one can explain. However, before the creation of STR, no one cared about this, just as, for example, now no one cares that the phenomenon of ball lightning has not been explained.

But at the beginning of the 20th century Joseph Larmor [2], Nobel Prize winner Hendrik Anton Lorenz [3], Jules Henri Poincaré [4], Nobel Prize winner Albert Einstein [5] and other outstanding scientists created the special theory of relativity, which rightly accepted to be considered an outstanding scientific achievement of physics of the 20th century, because it proposed the principle of relativity. And which is therefore now studied in all physics textbooks used in the educational process even at the most prestigious universities. However, in this theory, calculations using relativistic formulas, which were the final result of all reasoning, in some cases led to a result measured by imaginary numbers.

And this result already needed to be explained. After all, no one would need a theory that even its creators could not explain. But the authors of SRT did not know how to do this. And the fate of STO hung in the balance. But it was saved by the fact that an additional postulate was introduced into the SRT, called the principle of not exceeding the speed of light, from which it followed that quantities measured by imaginary numbers do not exist in nature. And therefore, there is no need to explain them.

This is the form in which SRT is still taught.

2. The physical reality of imaginary numbers.

But besides STR there are other sciences. Including the theory of electrical circuits, which is used in radio engineering, electrical engineering and computer science. Fundamental to this theory is Ohm's law [6], [7], discovered in 1826 for DC electrical circuits, which is now studied even in school physics textbooks. And in 1893, Charles Proteus Steinmetz proposed its interpretation of Ohm's law for alternating current electrical circuits [8], which is now used daily by millions of engineers around the world in their work. In this theory of electrical circuits, the imaginary resistances of capacitors and inductors, which can be measured by instruments, were recognized as actually physically existing. And if these imaginary resistances were recognized as physically unreal, as follows from SRT, then neither radio engineering, nor electrical engineering, nor computers, nor radio measuring instruments should exist.

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Fig. 1. In any radio-technical laboratory there are devices called frequency response meters, which prove the physical reality of imaginary and complex numbers by their mere existence

But they do exist. And thereby they prove the physical reality of imaginary numbers [9]-[33]. Consequently, by the existence of radio- and electrical engineering, the generally accepted version of SRT was refuted even before its creation. Other proofs of the physical reality of imaginary numbers have been published in [34]-[46]. Therefore, the logical conclusion is that the version of STR currently presented in all physics textbooks is incorrect [47]-[66].

3. Physical reality of invisible parallel universes

In the existing generally recognized version of SRT from its relativistic formulas and the principle of non-exceeding the speed of light also follows that in nature there is only our visible universe in which everything is measured only by real numbers. However, in the corrected version of SRT [67]-[74], from its relativistic formulas it follows that in our Multiverse [75]-[85], in addition to our visible universe, there are also about twenty other mutually invisible parallel universes

Fig. 2. Scheme of an astronomical experiment to detect invisible universes

And one can be convinced of their existence [86]-[91]. as a result of astronomical observations of the starry sky in portals [92]-[94], since the constellations in them will differ - and the further into the portal one penetrates, the greater the differences will be - from the constellations observed at the same time in the same region outside the portals. And since there are a lot of anomalous zones [95]-[98] on Earth, presumably being entrances to portals, some observatories have already are located in such anomalous zones. Like, for example, the main astronomical observatory of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, located in Golo-seyevsky forest 12 km from the center of Kyiv. Therefore, in order to verify the existence of neighboring invisible universes adjacent to our visible universe, it is enough to compare on a computer the observations of this observatory with the observations of neighboring observatories located outside the anomalous zones.

4. Why, despite all the refutations of the generally accepted version of SRT, set out in all physics textbooks, it continues to be taught.

But this simple and low-cost experiment, which in the most indisputable way will allow us to answer the question of whether there are invisible universes neighboring our visible universe, no one has done or is going to do. Obviously, because physicists do not need such an answer, since it will refute the version of SRT studied in textbooks.

The corrected version of SRT states that imaginary numbers are physically real and invisible universes exist. Therefore, having become convinced of the existence of invisible universes, we will have to admit that the corrected version of SRT is correct and once again be convinced that imaginary numbers actually physically exist. And then it will inevitably be necessary to explain their physical meaning of imaginary numbers. And this physical meanings is obvious - in addition to our visible world, there is an invisible world.

5. The existence of a physically real invisible world

However, the usefulness for science of the above experimental evidence of the physical reality of imaginary numbers goes beyond problems of correcting the version of SRT given in physics textbooks. From experimentally proven principle of the physical reality of imaginary numbers, one will inevitably have to conclude that the results of all studies described by imaginary numbers in all other exact sciences also are physically real.

And therefore, in the end, we will have to admit that in addition to our visible world, there is also a huge (most likely even much larger than our visible world) invisible world [99]-[106]. Indeed, in addition to the room in which we are now and which we see, there are a large number of other invisible to us rooms in other apartments, houses, cities and countries. The same situation is in space – in addition to our visible universe, in other dimensions there are about twenty other parallel universes of the hidden Multiverse that are invisible to us. And outside of our hidden Multiverse in the Hyperverses, there are many other invisible universes.

All world religions have long predicted the existence of such an invisible afterlife, where God and the souls of the dead dwell. Therefore, it is acceptable to assume that what these religions say about the world order, about the afterlife, is true. And that is why all of us, inhabitants of the planet Earth, now it is necessary to understand, accept and think about our afterlife future. And adjust our behavior accordingly.

6. Conclusion

The author hopes that the information presented in the article will be an incentive to unite the efforts of science and religions in their activities for the benefit of people.

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